

Nitroso Complexes of Lower Valent Rhenium

D. K. Hait and P. Bandyopadhyay

The paper describes the isolation and properties of several rhenium complexes viz., $[\text{ReCl}_3(\text{dipy})(\text{NO})]$, $[\text{ReCl}_3(\text{phen})(\text{NO})]$, $[\text{ReCl}(\text{dipy})_2(\text{NO})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ and $[\text{ReCl}(\text{phen})_2(\text{NO})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ where dipy and phen stand for 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline respectively. The non-electrolytes are insoluble in water and in common organic solvents but are soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid from which they can be reprecipitated unchanged. The cationic compounds are soluble in water, acetone and ethanol. All these are weakly paramagnetic at room temperature. The infra-red spectra of the non electrolytes show sharp bands at 1740 cm^{-1} (dipyridyl compound) and 1760 cm^{-1} (phenanthroline compound).

Sarkar and co-workers have reported the isolation of several interesting nitrosyl complexes of rhenium derived from the parent $\text{ReCl}_3(\text{NO})^{1,2}$. The present communication reports the isolation of a few nonelectrolytic and cationic complexes derived from the same parent using 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline ligands. These include $[\text{ReCl}_3(\text{dipy})(\text{NO})]$, $[\text{ReCl}_3(\text{phen})(\text{NO})]$, $[\text{ReCl}(\text{dipy})_2(\text{NO})]^{+2}$ and $[\text{ReCl}(\text{phen})_2(\text{NO})]^{+2}$

The nonelectrolytes can be prepared either from hydrated $\text{ReCl}_3(\text{NO})$ and the ligand or directly from the mono-dipyridyl and mono-phenanthroline salts of hexachloro-rhenate (IV) and nitric oxide (vide infra). The phenanthroline compound is snuff coloured and the dipyridyl compound is yellowish brown. These are very stable insoluble substances remaining unattacked on boiling with hydrochloric acid (concentrated or dilute) and dilute sulphuric acid. They are only slowly attacked by boiling with aqueous alkali, the solution showing the existence of NO_2^- ion derived from the nitroso group in the complex. They can be dissolved in cold concentrated sulphuric acid and reprecipitated unchanged by ice cold water at 0° . They are insoluble in most of the organic solvents, but soluble in dimethyl formamide and in boiling acetone. These compounds are slowly and incompletely converted to the cationic bis-complexes by refluxing with aqueous ligand hydrochloride. The same conversion can be effected by fusion of the nonelectrolyte with excess orthophenanthroline. The cationic compound cannot, however, be prepared with dipyridyl in this way.

These compounds are para-magnetic in nature, the effective magnetic moments (corrected for ligands) being 1.71 B.M. for the phenanthroline compound and 2.19 B.M. for the dipyridyl compound at 30° . The infrared spectra indicate a single sharp band at 1740 cm^{-1} for the dipyridyl compound and 1760 cm^{-1} for the phenanthroline compound in the nitric oxide stretching frequency region.

The cationic compounds can be prepared by refluxing the hydrated $\text{ReCl}_3(\text{NO})$ with the ligands in dilute hydrochloric acid medium. However, the best method for the preparation of the phenanthroline complex is to heat $(\text{phenH})_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ in a current of nitric oxide.

1. B. K. Sen, P. Bandyopadhyay and P. B. Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 496.
2. B. K. Sen, P. Bandyopadhyay and P. B. Sarkar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 227.

The dipyridyl compound cannot be prepared by this procedure which yields only the non-electrolytic species. The compounds are purified through the precipitation of sparingly soluble perchlorates.

The aqueous solutions of the chlorides are not quite stable and they produce dark coloured precipitates on standing. Insoluble chloroplatinates of the composition $[\text{ReCl}(\text{ligand})_2(\text{NO})] \text{PtCl}_6$ can be precipitated like perchlorates. The perchlorates are soluble in ethanol and acetone.

The effective magnetic moment for the perchlorate of the phenanthroline derivative is 1.15 B.M. and that for the dipyridyl derivative is 1.64 B.M. at 30°.

In the u.v.-visible absorption spectra in dilute aqueous solutions maxima were obtained at 17240 cm^{-1} (broad), 19760 cm^{-1} (sharp), 37310 cm^{-1} (sharp), 39220 cm^{-1} (shoulder), and 43860 cm^{-1} (sharp) for the phenanthroline compound and 17040 cm^{-1} (sharp), 21280 cm^{-1} (very broad), 32680 cm^{-1} (sharp), 40820 cm^{-1} (shoulder) and 44840 cm^{-1} (sharp) for the dipyridyl compound.

EXPERIMENTAL

The starting material was Johnson Matthey's 99.8% potassium perrhenate; (dipyH)H $[\text{ReCl}_6]$, (dipyH)₂ $[\text{ReCl}_6]$, (phenH)H $[\text{ReCl}_6]$ and (phenH)₂ $[\text{ReCl}_6]$ were prepared by following the method of Morgan and Davies³. These were dried in vacuum over concentrated sulphuric acid, 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline were of E. Merck's reagent quality.

The u.v.-visible absorption spectra were recorded in a Hilger's Uvispek spectrophotometer and the infrared spectra were recorded in a Perkin Elmer's model-421. Magnetic moments were determined by a Gouy balance.

For the purpose of analysis, the compounds were decomposed by fusion with sodium peroxide. Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as silver chloride and rhenium by electro-deposition. Nitrogen was estimated by micro-Duma's method.

Trichloro 2,2'-dipyridylnitrosorhenium(II)-[ReCl₃(dipy)(NO)]: 0.5 gm of dry yellow mono-dipyridyl salt of hexachlororhenate(IV) was finely powdered and taken in a porcelain boat. It was heated in a current of pure dry nitric oxide (prepared by reducing nitrous acid with ferrous sulphate). The system was previously freed from air by a stream of dry carbon dioxide. Heating was continued for an hour at a temperature of $240^\circ \pm 5^\circ$. The system was then cooled below 100° and the nitric oxide inside was driven out by chasing with carbon dioxide. The brown mass was then taken out and refluxed for 30 minutes with concentrated hydrochloric acid to remove any unchanged starting material. The solid was filtered, washed successively with water and ethanol. The air dried product was analysed. The yield was about 0.4 gm.

Found, Re 38.6, Cl 22.2, N 8.59 percent. The formula given requires Re 38.9, Cl 22.2, N 8.77 percent.

3. G. T. Morgan and G. R. Davies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1858.

Trichloro 1, 10-phenanthrolinenitrosorhenium(II) $[\text{ReCl}_3(\text{phen})(\text{NO})]$: This compound was prepared from mono-phenanthroline salt of hexachlororhenate(IV) exactly in the same way as the dipyridyl derivative. The yield was also similar.

Found, Re 36.3, Cl 21.6, N 8.40 percent. The given formula requires Re 37.0, Cl 21.2, N 8.35 percent.

Monochloro bis 2,2'-dipyridylnitrosorhenic (II) perchlorate— $[\text{ReCl}(\text{dipy})_2(\text{NO})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$; Hydrated $\text{ReCl}_3(\text{NO})$ was prepared by the method of Sarkar and co-workers¹. On refluxing a solution of this with dipyridyl hydrochloride in aqueous hydrochloric acid various unidentified and insoluble products were obtained along with the desired one and it was observed that acid concentration was an important factor in the yield. Best result was obtained by boiling 0.5 gm nitroso-chloride, (dried in vacuum over concentrated sulphuric acid), 0.5 gm dipyridyl hydrochloride and 0.5 ml concentrated hydrochloric acid in 20 ml water. Refluxing was continued for 6 hrs when a deep blue solution resulted. This was evaporated to dryness on water bath and the residue was extracted with water. To this a saturated solution of sodium perchlorate was added. The deep blue precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water, dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid and analysed. The yield was 0.2 gm.

Found, Re 24.0, Cl 13.1, N 9.0 percent. The formula given requires Re 24.4, Cl 13.9, N 9.2 percent.

Monochloro bis 1, 10-phenanthrolinenitrosorhenic (II) perchlorate : $[\text{ReCl}(\text{phen})_2(\text{NO})](\text{ClO}_4)_2$: 0.5 gm of dry powdered $(\text{phenH})_2[\text{ReCl}_6]$ was heated in an experimental arrangement as in the case of non-electrolytic compounds. The mass was kept at a temperature of $240^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ for 20 mins. After cooling and removing the nitric oxide from the system, it was extracted with absolute ethanol and refluxed for 30 mins. The blue-violet extract was filtered from a small quantity of black residue and evaporated on water bath. The dry mass was repeatedly extracted with acetone which removed a small quantity of a violet substance. The final residue still contained some phenanthroline hydrochloride which could not be easily removed. It was therefore, dissolved in water and a saturated solution of sodium perchlorate was added. The blue-violet crystalline precipitate was filtered, washed with cold water, dried in vacuum over sulphuric acid and analysed. The yield was about 0.3 gm.

Found, Re 22.2, Cl 13.2, N 8.10 percent. The formula given requires Re 23.0, Cl 13.1, N 8.60 percent.

DISCUSSION

The cationic compounds are expected to exist in cis and trans forms. As a matter of fact, the chlorides exist in two coloured varieties for both the compounds. The phenanthroline compound exists in blue and violet varieties but the violet one is always obtained in such a low yield that its characterisation has not been possible so far. The dipyridyl compound exists in blue and green forms, of which the green product is soluble in acetone. But any attempt for its isolation in the solid state converts it to the blue variety. For

the non-electrolytic compounds, besides the geometrical isomers, coordination polymers exist. The compounds of the composition $[\text{ReCl}(\text{ligand})_2(\text{NO})]$ $[\text{ReCl}_5(\text{NO})]$ have been prepared by the double decomposition of the cationic complexes with K_2 $[\text{ReCl}_6(\text{NO})]$. These almost black substances are very slightly soluble in hot water.

Our best thanks are due to Prof. P. B. Sarkar, and Dr. B. K. Sen, for their keen interest in the investigation.

Department of Chemistry,
University College of Science,
Calcutta-9.

Received July 3, 1970